

FINITE DIFFERENCE METHOD FOR THE ANALYSIS OF FILAMENT WOUND COMPOSITE SHELLS

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SUMMARY: The present paper deals with the application of finite difference method to the analysis of thin-walled composite structures. The mechanical models and numerical techniques are developed for laminated composite structures reinforced by various elements and layers. The numerical solutions of the static problems of thermoelasticity are discussed for composite filament wound orthotropic shells of revolution.

All of the methods are based on the applied theory of thin-walled composite structures which allows for transverse interlaminar shear strains. The equations of the shell theory of this type were derived on the basis of three-dimensional theory of elasticity (see: Vasiliev [1], Vorobey, Morozov, and Tatarnikov [2]).

KEYWORDS: filament wound composite shells, finite difference method, thermoelasticity, transverse shear strain

INTRODUCTION

Composite materials and structures can be designed to meet the special set of requirements. The composite thin-walled structures operating under conditions of both the high-temperature heating and mechanical loading are used for some aerospace applications. Carbon-carbon composites are most appropriate materials in this case. In the present paper the filament wound composite shells of revolution are considered. They consist of the number of elementary unidirectionally reinforced helical layers with different angles of orientation. The main parameters describing a particular laminated composite structure are the mechanical and physical properties of unidirectional elementary layer, fibre orientation, thickness distribution, stacking sequences, and the number of layers. For the structures considered the elementary layer consists of two plies symmetrically oriented at angles of $\pm \phi$. In order to take into account all of the main features of the material, structure and operational conditions the appropriate mechanical models and mathematical approaches should be developed. In this paper the variant of refined applied theory of thermoelastic composite shells is used as the basis for modelling procedure and analysis of stress-strain state. The mechanical properties of composite elementary layers were obtained experimentally as a result of special mechanical tests. The finite difference method of approximation has been used in order to calculate the displacements of the shell, stress and strain distributions for elementary layers of composite material. Cubic spline interpolation has been used to define the data for numerical analysis during the computational process.

THEORY OF THIN-WALLED COMPOSITE STRUCTURES

Composite shells of revolution with the symmetrical structure of reinforcement are considered. The shell is produced by filament winding with the angles of fibre orientation $\pm \phi(y)$ to the meridian line of the initial surface of the shell (see Fig.1). The type of fibres and matrix is the same for the whole shell. It gives the opportunity to use simplified constitutive equations relating force and moment resultants to the strain components of the initial (middle) surface. The reinforced layer is referred to a co-ordinate system coincided with the layer's symmetry axes (1,2,3). Axes 1 is directed along the fibre orientation, axes 2 defines the transversal direction, and axes 3 is orthogonal to the plane (1,2).

Figure 1. Filament wound shell of revolution

The shell is referred to a cylindrical coordinate system as presented in Fig.1. The coordinates α , β are the curvilinear surface coordinates coinciding with the principal directions (longitudinal and circumferential respectively) of the middle surface of the shell.

The equilibrium equations are presented as follows:

$$\frac{d(rN_\alpha)}{dy} - \bar{r}N_\beta - \frac{rr''}{1+(r')^2} Q_\alpha = 0, \quad \frac{d(rM_\alpha)}{dy} - r'M_\beta - r[1+(r')^2]^{1/2} Q_\alpha = 0, \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{d(rQ_\alpha)}{dy} + \frac{rr''}{1+(r')^2} N_\alpha - N_\beta + r[1+(r')^2]^{1/2} p(y) = 0,$$

where N_α , N_β , Q_α , M_α , M_β are the stress resultants; the y-axis is the axis of the shell ; $r(y)$ is the radius of cross-section; $r' = dr/dy$. The strain-displacement relationships can be written as

$$\begin{aligned}\varepsilon_\alpha &= u'[1+(r')^2]^{-1/2} - r''w[1+(r')^2]^{-3/2}, & \varepsilon_\beta &= (r'u+w)[1+(r')^2]^{-1/2} / r, \\ \kappa_\alpha &= \theta'_\alpha[1+(r')^2]^{-1/2}, & \kappa_\beta &= r'\theta_\alpha[1+(r')^2]^{-1/2} / r, \\ \varphi_\alpha &= \theta_\alpha + w'[1+(r')^2]^{-1/2} + r''u[1+(r')^2]^{-3/2},\end{aligned}\quad (2)$$

where u is the displacement of the initial surface along the axis α , w is the displacement orthogonal to the plane which is tangent to the initial surface of the shell, θ_α is the angle of rotation of the element which is orthogonal to the tangent plane; $\varepsilon_\alpha, \varepsilon_\beta, \kappa_\alpha, \kappa_\beta$ are the strain components, ψ_α is the transverse shear strain. In the case considered in this paper constitutive equations of thermoelasticity are given in the form

$$N_\alpha = C_{11}\varepsilon_\alpha + C_{12}\varepsilon_\beta - T_\alpha^{(0)}, \quad N_\beta = C_{12}\varepsilon_\alpha + C_{22}\varepsilon_\beta - T_\beta^{(0)}, \quad (3)$$

$$M_\alpha = D_{11}\kappa_\alpha + D_{12}\kappa_\beta - T_\alpha^{(1)}, \quad M_\beta = D_{21}\kappa_\alpha + D_{22}\kappa_\beta - T_\beta^{(1)}, \quad Q_\alpha = C_{55}\psi_\alpha,$$

where

$$C_{mn} = h\bar{B}_{mn}, \quad D_{mn} = h^3\bar{B}_{mn} / 12 \quad (m, n = 1, 2); \quad C_{55} = hG_{\alpha\gamma}; \quad T_{\alpha,\beta}^{(k)} = \int_{-h/2}^{h/2} \bar{B}_{mi} t^k d\gamma; \quad k = 0, 1;$$

In these formulas \bar{B}_{mn} , \bar{B}_{mi} , are the stiffness and the thermal coefficients of the layer reinforced under the angle ϕ (these coefficients can be calculated for given material structure using the known equations of mechanics of composite materials [1], [2]); C_{55} - is the coefficient of transversal shear stiffness and $G_{\alpha\gamma}$ is the transversal shear modulus. The modulus $G_{\alpha\gamma}$ can be presented in terms of the shear moduli G_{13}, G_{23} of the unidirectionally reinforced material. These moduli should be determined experimentally or calculated using the micro-mechanical models of composites.

The equations (1)-(3) can be rearranged to the following system

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{d(\bar{r}Q_\alpha)}{d\bar{y}} + \frac{\bar{r}''\bar{r}}{a^2} N_\alpha + r_0\bar{r}p_0\bar{p}(\bar{y})a - \frac{C_{12}}{r_0a} (u' - \frac{w\bar{r}''}{a^2}) - \frac{C_{22}u\bar{r}'}{r_0\bar{r}a} - \frac{C_{22}w}{r_0\bar{r}a} + T_\beta^{(0)} &= 0, \\ \frac{d(\bar{r}M_\alpha)}{d\bar{y}} - \frac{D_{12}\bar{r}'}{ar_0} \theta'_\alpha - \frac{D_{22}(\bar{r}')^2}{ar_0\bar{r}} \theta'_\alpha + r_0\bar{r}aQ_\alpha + T_\beta^{(1)}\bar{r}' &= 0, \\ \frac{d\theta_\alpha}{d\bar{y}} + \frac{D_{12}\bar{r}'}{D_{11}\bar{r}} \theta_\alpha - \frac{r_0a}{D_{11}} (M_\alpha + T_\alpha^{(1)}) &= 0, \quad \frac{dw}{d\bar{y}} + r_0a\theta_\alpha - \frac{\bar{r}''}{a^2} u - \frac{r_0a}{C_{55}} Q_\alpha &= 0,\end{aligned}\quad (4)$$

$$\frac{du}{d\bar{y}} + \frac{C_{12}\bar{r}'}{C_{11}} u + \left(\frac{C_{12}}{C_{11}\bar{r}} - \frac{\bar{r}''}{a^2} \right) w - \frac{r_0a}{C_{11}} (N_\alpha + T_\alpha^{(0)}) = 0,$$

$$N_\alpha - \bar{r}'Q_\alpha = p_0r_0 \frac{a}{\bar{r}'} \int_{\bar{y}_a}^{\bar{y}} \bar{p}(\bar{y})\bar{r}'\bar{r}d\bar{y}$$

where $\bar{y} = y / r_0$; $\bar{r} = r / r_0$; $\bar{p} = p / p_0$; $a^2 = 1 + (\bar{r}')^2$; r_0 , p_0 , are the specified parameters of the shell and load respectively. The equations were accomplished by the following boundary conditions:

$$u = 0; w = 0; \theta_\alpha = 0 \text{ for } y = y_0; \quad N_\alpha = 0; Q_\alpha = 0; M_\alpha = 0 \text{ for } y = y_\alpha. \quad (5)$$

If we have solution of the system (4) the strain components of the initial surface of the shell can be calculated using equations (2). After that we can calculate the strains e_α , e_β for any point of the wall of the structure by the following way

$$e_\alpha = \varepsilon_\alpha + \gamma \kappa_\alpha, \quad e_\beta = \varepsilon_\beta + \gamma \kappa_\beta.$$

The strain components for elementary unidirectional layer can be calculated as follows

$$\begin{aligned} \varepsilon_1 &= e_\alpha \cos^2 \phi + e_\beta \sin^2 \phi, & \varepsilon_2 &= e_\alpha \sin^2 \phi + e_\beta \cos^2 \phi, \\ \varepsilon_{12} &= (e_\beta - e_\alpha) \sin 2\phi \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

Normal stress σ_1 acting along the fibres, normal stress σ_2 acting in the direction orthogonal to fibre orientation, and shear stress τ_{12} can be calculated for each elementary layer and cross-section of the shell using the following equations

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_1 &= \bar{E}_1 (\varepsilon_1 + \mu_{12} \varepsilon_2) - \bar{E}_1 t (\alpha_1 + \mu_{12} \alpha_2), & \sigma_2 &= \bar{E}_2 (\varepsilon_2 + \mu_{21} \varepsilon_1) - \bar{E}_2 t (\alpha_2 + \mu_{21} \alpha_1), \\ \tau_{12} &= G_{12} \varepsilon_{12} \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

where $\bar{E}_{1,2} = \bar{E}_{1,2} / (1 - \mu_{12} \mu_{21})$, $\bar{E}_{1,2}$ - are the longitudinal and transverse Young's moduli of unidirectionally reinforced material respectively, G_{12} - is the shear modulus, t - change of temperature at the given point of the wall, α_1, α_2 - are the coefficients of thermal expansion along the fibres and in the orthogonal direction respectively, and μ_{12}, μ_{21} are the Poisson's ratios. The stresses acting in the wall of the shell can be calculated in terms of the stress resultants from the following equations [2]

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_\alpha &= N_\alpha / h + 12 M_\alpha \gamma / h^3, & \sigma_\beta &= N_\beta / h + 12 M_\beta \gamma / h^3, \\ \tau_{\alpha\beta} &= N_{\alpha\beta} / h + 12 M_{\alpha\beta} \gamma / h^3, & \tau_{\alpha\gamma} &= (1.5 / h - 6\gamma^2 / h^3) Q_\alpha \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

where $\tau_{\alpha\gamma}$ - is the transversal shear stress.

The approach presented above has been used for the analysis of stress-strain state of carbon-carbon composite shells of revolution operating in the conditions of high-temperature heating jointly with the different types of mechanical loading.

NUMERICAL METHODS

The finite difference method has been used in order to obtain numerical solution of the problem determined by equations (4) and boundary conditions (5). The system (4) was approximated by the first order finite differences. Cubic spline interpolation was implemented to represent the geometry and shape of the shell $\bar{r}(\bar{y})$, thickness of the wall $h(\bar{y})$, internal pressure distribution $\bar{p}(\bar{y})$ and the pattern of filament winding $\phi(\bar{y})$ in the following general form

$$S(\bar{y}) = \sum_{p=0}^3 Q_{pq} (\bar{y} - y_q)^p; \quad \bar{y}_{q-1} \leq \bar{y} \leq \bar{y}_q$$

where $\bar{y} = y / r_0$, $\bar{p} = p / p_0$; r_0 is the radius of the initial cross-section of the shell (see Fig.1), and p_0 is the value of the pressure for the same cross-section. Dispelling method has been used in order to determine the coefficients of cubic spline Q_{pq} . As the result we obtain the system of linear algebraic equations. The system contains $6(n+1)$ variables, namely $u_i, w_i, \theta_{\alpha i}, N_{\alpha i}, Q_{\alpha i}, M_{\alpha i}$ for the $(n+1)$ points and consists of $5n$ equations written for the $n+1$ points on the basis of the first five equations from the system (4). The sixth equation of the system (4) which has been integrated in explicit form gives another $n+1$ algebraic equations and five equations have been obtained from the boundary conditions (5) as follows:

$$u_1 = 0, w_1 = 0, \theta_{\alpha 1} = 0 \text{ for the point 1,}$$

$$\text{and } Q_{\alpha_{n+1}} = 0, M_{\alpha_{n+1}} = 0 \text{ for the point number } n+1.$$

Resulting system of linear algebraic equations has the band type matrix and solution of this system gives the values of basic unknown functions $u(\bar{y}), w(\bar{y}), \theta_{\alpha}(\bar{y}), N_{\alpha}(\bar{y}), Q_{\alpha}(\bar{y}), M_{\alpha}(\bar{y})$ for $n+1$ points of the analysis (radial cross-sections of the shell). Corresponding stresses and strains are calculated according to equations (6) - (7).

NUMERICAL RESULTS

Analysis of the cylindrical composite shell loaded by uniformly distributed internal pressure has been used in order to verify computer algorithm and optimise parameters of finite difference grid. Results of calculations were compared with the analytical solution. As an example of application of the method suggested a numerical analysis for filament wound carbon- carbon composite shell of revolution has been produced. Mechanical characteristics of the unidirectional carbon-carbon composite were determined experimentally: $E_1 = 157.4$ GPa, $E_2 = 19.2$ GPa, $G_{12} = 9.0$ GPa, $\mu_{21} = 0.3$.

For unidirectionally reinforced material $G_{12} = G_{13}$. In order to calculate transversal shear modulus $G_{\alpha\gamma}$ we need to know modulus G_{13} . It could be shown that for unidirectional composite the following equation is appropriate [3]

$$G_{23} = G_m \frac{\kappa_m + \xi + \eta \frac{G_m}{G_f}}{\eta \kappa_m + (1 + \xi \kappa_m) \frac{G_m}{G_f}}$$

In this equation G_f, G_m are the shear moduli of fibres and matrix respectively; ξ and $\eta = 1 - \xi$ are the volume contents of the fibres and matrix ; $\kappa_m = 3 - 4\mu_m$, where μ_m is the Poisson' ratio for matrix material. Using the experimental values for E_1 and E_2 we can find the values E_m and ξ for specified material. For carbon-carbon material considered in this paper $G_{23} = 9349$ MPa (Young's modulus for fibres was assumed to be equal to 250 GPa). The geometry of the shell and pressure distribution are shown in Figure 2.

Fig.2: Geometry of the shell and load distribution ($\bar{r} = r / r_0$)

Filament winding pattern function and thickness distribution are presented in Fig. 3. Some results of numerical solution are presented in Fig.4 and Fig.5. In Fig.4 normal displacement distribution $\bar{w}(\bar{y})$ of the shell is shown. Distribution of the stresses acting in the elementary layers of material are given in Fig.5. The main feature of carbon-carbon material produced by filament winding is the very low tensile transverse strength (for material discussed this mechanical characteristic is equal to 6.6 MPa). According to this the distribution of the transverse stresses over the structure is of significant interest. The results of calculation of transverse stresses σ_2 and shear stresses τ_{12} are presented in Fig.5 for both external and internal surfaces of the shell . As shown in Fig.5 the level of values of tensile transversal stresses is quite high and practically determines the strength of the shell for given load.

Fig.3 Filament winding pattern and thickness distribution

Fig.4 Distribution of the stresses in the elementary layer: $\sigma_2^i, \tau_{12}^i, \sigma_2^e, \tau_{12}^e$ - are the transverse and shear stresses for the internal (i) and external (e) surface of the shell.

Fig.5 Normal displacements of the shell

CONCLUSIONS

The method presented in the paper gives the possibility to produce stress-strain state analysis of thermoloaded composite shells of revolution. Numerical technique and algorithm implemented were verified and tested using the exact analytical solution obtained for the cylindrical shell. This solution has been used in order to optimise the parameters of finite difference discretization as well. Numerical analysis of carbon-carbon composite shell of revolution has been produced and the displacements, stresses, and strains were calculated. The numerical results obtained allow to estimate strength and stiffness of the shell. Such an assessment of the failure could be produced on the level of elementary reinforcing composite layer. All the necessary information for it could be obtained as the result of computational process. The method presented in the paper could be implemented as a part of optimisation procedure as well. In this case it can be used as a method of direct analysis of mechanical response of composite structure to be optimised.

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